

LEXICAL PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF STYLISTIC CONNOTATION

Ergasheva Nilufar Usar qizi

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. The connotations of a language expression are pragmatic effects that arise from encyclopaedic knowledge about its denotation (or reference) and also from experiences, beliefs, and prejudices about the contexts in which the expression is typically used. The connotation of a language expression is clearly distinct from its sense, denotation and reference.

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So far as I am aware, there has been no extended discussion elsewhere of the fact that connotations are pragmatic effects, though it is often implicit; for instance in the following accounts of connotation: ‘The use of synonyms and antonyms clarifies connotational choices as between, say, pejorative and euphemistic usages’; ‘The set of associations implied by a word in addition to its literal meaning’; and according to Löbner, connotations are conventional associations activated by an expression as additions to its ‘primary lexical meaning’. In logic, the term *connotation* is more or less synonymous with ‘intension’ or what many linguists call ‘sense’.

The social and expressive information about Speaker’s evaluation is central here. Since such connotative meanings are related to Speaker’s real-world experience, they will vary from community to community to a greater extent than denotative meanings. Insulting comparisons of people with animals rely on certain conventionally ascribed behaviours, i.e. on encyclopaedic knowledge, experiences, beliefs, and prejudices about the animal. These pragmatic effects attach to the animal name and endow it with the potential for figurative application to humans that are

thereby ascribed similar behaviours. There are semantic constraints such as that names of female animals can normally be used only in naming or addressing women and male homosexuals: e.g. a *cat* is typically a “vicious and/or scratchy woman”; but a *pussy* is used (mostly in America) to insult a male for being “effeminate, homosexual” and occasionally of a female for having a “weak character” (it is also slang for a *femme* “lesbian who adopts the feminine role”); a *bitch* is a “(usually nasty) woman held in contempt”; a *vixen* is a “cunning, perhaps sneaky, woman”; *cow* and *sow* don’t differ much, they generally denote a “woman disliked, who is typically doltish” – and there are connotations of being fat, too, cf. the commonly used *fat cow/sow*. Some animal names are typically used of men: *mongrel*, *cur* or *swine* denotes a “vicious, nasty fellow, held in contempt” (comparable with *cat* and *bitch* of women); a *fox* denotes a “cunning man”, compare *vixen* (*foxy lady* is a compliment to the sexiness of a woman); a *bull* is for a “big, often rather clumsy, man”; *stallion*, *goat* or *ram* can be used of a “horny/randy man”. Figurative extensions like animal names applied to humans seem to rely on the pragmatic effects of their connotation to a greater extent than on sense or denotation. Note that although connotation is distinct from denotation, it is to some extent dependent on denotation as the objects of knowledge or belief.

Proper names too have connotations i.e. pragmatic effects that constrain the way they are given and used. For example, *Mike* and *Michael* can have the same reference but usually have different connotations as do Russian alternative personal names such as *Katerina*, *Katen’ka*, *Katjuša*, *Kat’ka*, *Katjuša*, *Katja*, *Katënok*, and *Katënyš*, see Wierzbicka. Just as *John* is an unsuitable name for your new-born daughter, so is *Springtime in Paris* an inappropriate name for a 1200cc Harley-Davidson motorbike or an auto-repair shop. *Wheels and Deals* might be a good name for a used car mart, but not for a new strain of corn, nor for a maternity boutique. People are well aware of these facts, and marketing folk exploit such knowledge to

the full. Lehrer reviewed the proper names of car models, rock bands, beauty salons, streets, and university buildings and found that what Kripke dubs 'baptisms' are mostly systematic, and each genre develops its own naming themes and styles based on connotation.

I have argued in this paper that the connotations of a language expression are pragmatic effects that arise from encyclopaedic knowledge about its denotation (or reference) and also from experiences, beliefs, and prejudices about the contexts in which the expression is typically used. The connotation of a language expression is distinct from its sense, denotation and reference. Identifying the connotations of a term is to identify the community attitude towards it. Connotation is intimately involved with notions of appropriateness in language use that conditions the choice of vocabulary (including proper names) and style of address. Connotation is involved in choosing expressions that upgrade, downgrade and insult. It plays a part in the loaded weapon of dysphemism and the euphemistic avoidance of dispreferred expressions judged discriminatory, blasphemous, obscene, or merely tasteless. Reactions to connotation are pragmatic effects that motivate semantic extension and the generation of new vocabulary. Connotation is a thoroughly pragmatic category of meaning.

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